

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1855	Eduard Meyer	1875	1875	1920		German Ancient historian, Egyptologist and ancient Orientalist	1855-1930
1855	Friedrich Bechtel	1876	1876	1924		German philologist and linguist of Indo-European languages, known for his research of Greek dialects	1855-1924
1855	August Sauer	1877	1877	1926		Austrian Germanist and literary historian	1855-1926
1855	Edmond Pottier	1877	1877	1915		French art historian and archaeologist who was instrumental in establishing the Corpus vasorum antiquorum	1855-1934
1855	Kuno Francke	1878	1878	1929		German-American professor of history and German culture and curator of the Germanic Museum	1855-1930
1855	Franz Muncker	1878	1878	1926		German literary historian	1855-1926
1855	Henry Ling Roth	1878		1924		British English anthropologist and museum curator, active in Australia	1855-1925
1855	Hermann Collitz	1878	1878	1927		German historical linguist and Indo-Europeanist	1855-1935
1855	Otto Schrader	1878	1878	1919		German philologist best known for his work on the history of German and Proto-Indo-European vocabulary dealing with various aspects of material culture	1855-1919
1855	Jakob Minor	1878	1878	1912		Austrian literary critic	1855-1912
1855	Alfred Cort Haddon	1879	1879	1926		British influential anthropologist and ethnologist	1855-1940
1855	Roman Zawiliński	1880	No	1916		Polish linguist, pedagogue and ethnographer, Founder and editor of Poradnik Językowy	1855-1932
1855	Emil Levy	1880	1880	1917		German romanist, provenalist and lexicographer	1855-1917
1855	Wilhelm Grube	1880	1880	1908		German sinologist and ethnographer	1855-1908
1855	Barrett Wendell	1885		1917		American academic known for a series of textbooks	1855-1921
1855	Leopold Janikowski	1886	No	1932		Polish explorer and ethnographer	1855-1942
1855	Francis James Gillen	1897		1912		Australian anthropologist and ethnologist	1855-1912
1855	Vladimir Jochelson	1900		1922		Russian-American ethnographer and researcher of the indigenous peoples of the Russian North	1855-1937
1856	Marcelino Menéndez y Pelayo	1875	1875	1912		Spanish scholar, historian and literary critic	1856-1912
1856	Cecil Bendall	1876		1906		British English scholar, a professor of Sanskrit	1856-1906

1856	Aleksander Brückner	1876	1876	1924	Polish scholar of Slavic languages and literatures (Slavistics), philologist, lexicographer and historian of literature	1856-1939
1856	Wilhelm Geiger	1878	1878	1942	German Orientalist in the fields of Indo-Iranian languages and the history of Iran and Sri Lanka	1856-1943
1856	Henri Lebègue	1878		1938	French palaeographer, director of studies at the École pratique des hautes études	1856-1938
1856	Karl Lamprecht	1878	1878	1915	German historian who specialized in German art and economic history	1856-1915
1856	Friedrich Kluge	1878	1878	1926	German philologist and educator	1856-1926
1856	Ernst Maass	1879	1879	1924	German classical philologist	1856-1929
1856	Gotthold Gundermann	1880	1880	1921	German classical philologist	1856-1921
1856	Theophilus Pinches	1880		1932	British pioneer British assyriologist	1856-1934
1856	Max Kaluza	1881	1881	1921	German scholar of English philology	1856-1921
1856	Ridolfo Livi	1882		1917	Italian anthropologist	1856-1920
1856	Albert Eichhorn	1883	1883	1913	German Protestant theologian	1856-1926
1856	Robert Dick Wilson	1883	No	1920	American linguist and Presbyterian scholar who devoted his life to prove the reliability of the Hebrew Bible	1856-1930
1856	Karl Krumbacher	1883	1883	1909	German scholar who was an expert on Byzantine Greek language, literature, history and culture	1856-1909
1856	Elsdon Best	1912		1925	New Zealand ethnographer who made important contributions to the study of the Māori of New Zealand	1856-1931
1856	Christopher Johnston	1894	1894	1914	American physician and Assyriologist, a scholar of ancient Mesopotamia	1856-1914
1857	Ferdinand de Saussure	1878	1880	1913	Swiss linguist and semiotician	1857-1913
1857	Antoine Thomas	1878		1933	French linguist	1857-1935
1857	Rudolf Thurneysen	1879	1879	1923	Swiss linguist and Celticist	1857-1940
1857	Otto Crusius	1879	1879	1918	German classical philologist	1857-1918
1857	Arthur Henry Bullen	1880	No	1920	British editor and publisher, a specialist in 16th and 17th century literature, and founder of the Shakespeare Head Press	1857-1920
1857	Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje	1880	1880	1927	Dutch scholar of Oriental cultures and languages and Advisor on Native Affairs to the colonial government of the Dutch East Indies (now Indonesia)	1857-1936

1857	Adolf Jülicher	1880	1880	1923	German scholar and biblical exegete	1857-1938
1857	Frank Hamilton Cushing	1881		1900	American anthropologist and ethnologist	1857-1900
1857	M. Carey Thomas	1882	1882	1922 w	American educator, suffragist, and linguist	1857-1935
1857	Leon Piniński	1883		1930	Polish scholar, diplomat, art historian and politician	1857-1938
1857	Emanuel Löwy	1883		1938	Austrian classical archaeologist and theorist who employed the methodology of universal psychological sources of form in his work	1857-1938
1857	Lucien Lévy-Bruhl	1884	1884	1927	French scholar trained in philosophy who furthered anthropology with his contributions to the budding fields of sociology and ethnology	1857-1939
1857	Erik Brate	1884	1884	1922	Swedish linguist and runologist	1857-1924
1857	Herbert Weir Smyth	1884	1884	1919	American classical scholar	1857-1937
1857	Paul Shorey	1884	1884	1927	American classical scholar	1857-1934
1857	Wilhelm Cloetta	1884	1884	1911	German Romance philologist and medievalist	1857-1911
1857	E. A. Wallis Budge	1885		1924	British English Egyptologist, Orientalist, and philologist who worked for the British Museum and published numerous works on the ancient Near East	1857-1934
1857	Stepanos Malkhasyants	1885		1947	Armenian academician, philologist, linguist, and lexicographer	1857-1947
1857	Zelia Nuttall	1886	No	1910	American archaeologist and anthropologist specialised in pre-Aztec Mexican cultures and pre-Columbian manuscripts	1857-1933
1857	Ioan Bianu	1887		1932	Austrian-Romanian philologist and bibliographer	1857-1935
1857	Claude Hermann Walter Johns	1888		1920	British Assyriologist and Church of England clergyman	1857-1920
1857	Ernest Langlois	1888	1888	1924	French medievalist, professor at the University of Lille	1857-1924
1857	Carl Meinhof	1890		1936	German linguist and one of the first linguists to study African languages	1857-1944
1857	Francis La Flesche	1893		1929	American first professional Native American ethnologist	1857-1932
1858	Juan Menéndez Pidal	1880		1915	Spanish archivist, juriconsult, historian, and poet	1858-1915
1858	Jan Bołoz Antoniewicz	1880	1880	1922	Polish historian and theoretician of Armenian art	1858-1922
1858	Anton Elter	1880	1880	1925	German classical philologist	1858-1925
1858	Eduard Schwartz	1880	1880	1936	German classical philologist	1858-1940

1858	Vaman Shivram Apte	1881		1892	Indian lexicographer and a professor of Sanskrit at Pune's Fergusson College	1858-1892
1858	Max Manilius	1881	1881	1927	German medievalist and Latin scholar	1858-1933
1858	Paul Haupt	1881		1926	German-American Semitic scholar, one of the pioneers of Assyriology in the United States	1858-1926
1858	Franz Boas	1881	1881	1936	German-American anthropologist and a pioneer of modern anthropology ("Father of American Anthropology")	1858-1942
1858	Rudolf Ernst Brünnow	1882	1882	1917	German-American orientalist and philologist	1858-1917
1858	Charles E. Bennett	1882	No	1921	American classic philologist, professor of Latin	1858-1921
1858	Jiří Polívka	1882	1882	1928	Czech linguist, slavist, literary historian and folklorist	1858-1933
1858	Herman Frederik Carel ten Kate	1882	1882	1919	Dutch anthropologist	1858-1931
1858	Julián Ribera	1884	1896	1927	Spanish Arabist and academic	1858-1934
1858	Kuno Meyer	1884	1884	1914	German scholar, distinguished in the field of Celtic philology and literature	1858-1919
1858	Karl Praechter	1885	1885	1926	German classical philologist	1858-1933
1858	Edward Schröder	1885	1885	1937	German Germanist and mediaevalist	1858-1942
1858	Émile Durkheim	1885	1893	1917	French sociologist	1858-1917
1858	Henri Hyvernat	1886		1922	French-American Coptologist, Semitist and orientalist	1858-1941
1858	Gustaf Kossinna	1887	1887	1930	German philologist and archaeologist	1858-1931
1858	David Samuel Margoliouth	1888	1888	1937	British English orientalist	1858-1940
1858	Jean-Vincent Scheil	1890		1940	French Dominican scholar and Assyriologist	1858-1940
1858	Frank Justus Miller	1892	1892	1925	American leading classicist, translator, and university administrator in the late 19th and early 20th centuries	1858-1938
1858	William Ridgeway	1892	No	1919	British-Irish classical scholar and the Disney Professor of Archaeology at Cambridge University	1858-1926
1858	Charles Mills Gayley	1893		1932	American professor of English, the Classics, and Academic Dean of the University of California at Berkeley	1858-1932
1858	Juan Vucetich	1895		1925	Croatian-Argentine anthropologist and police official who pioneered the use of fingerprinting	1858-1925
1858	Charles Hill-Tout	1895		1937	British-Canadian ethnologist and folklorist	1858-1944
1858	Henry Watson Fowler	1900		1933	British English schoolmaster, lexicographer and commentator on the usage of the English language	1858-1933

1859 Carl Bezold	1880	1880	1922	German orientalist	1859-1922
1859 Tadeusz Stefan Zieliński	1880	1880	1935	Polish prominent classical philologist, historian, translator of Sophocles, Euripides and other classical authors into Russian	1859-1944
1859 Georg Wissowa	1880	1880	1924	German classical philologist	1859-1931
1859 Konrad Burdach	1880		1936	German Germanist, literature critic	1859-1936
1859 Alexandru Philippide	1881	1881	1933	Romanian linguist and philologist	1859-1933
1859 Heinrich Schenkl	1881	1881	1919	Austrian classical philologist	1859-1919
1859 Gustav Roethe	1881	1881	1926	German philologist	1859-1926
1859 Edmund Hauler	1882	1882	1941	Austrian classical philologist	1859-1941
1859 Hans von Arnim	1882	1882	1930	German-Austrian classical philologist, who specialized in studies of Plato and Aristotle	1859-1931
1859 Friedrich Marx	1882	1882	1927	German classical philologist	1859-1941
1859 Morris H. Morgan	1883	No	1910	American professor of classical philology	1859-1910
1859 Berthold Wiese	1883	1925	1932	German Romance philologist, who specialized in Italian language and literature	1859-1932
1859 Hermann Volrath Hilprecht	1883	1883	1911	German-American Assyriologist and archaeologist	1859-1925
1859 Lazăr Șăineanu	1883		1922	French-Romanian philologist, linguist, folklorist and cultural historian	1859-1934
1859 Camille Jullian	1883	1883	1930	French historian, philologist, archaeologist and historian of French literature	1859-1933
1859 Paul Passy	1884		1926	French linguist, founder of the International Phonetic Association	1859-1940
1859 Bruno Keil	1884	1884	1916	German classical philologist	1859-1916
1859 Friedrich Salomon Krauss	1885		1938	Croatian-Austrian Jewish sexologist, ethnographer, folklorist, and Slavist	1859-1938
1859 John Napoleon Brinton Hewitt	1886	No	1937	American linguist and ethnographer	1859-1937
1859 Rafael Díez de la Cortina y Olaeta	1886	No	1927	Spanish-American linguist (first person to introduce sound recording into the teaching of foreign languages , for which he started a related business in the 1890s)	1859-1939
1859 L. L. Zamenhof	1886		1917	Polish ophthalmologist, linguist and the inventor of the international language Esperanto	1859-1917
1859 Charles Chewings	1886		1937	Australian geologist and anthropologist	1859-1937

1859 Anthony Ashley Bevan	1887		1928	British orientalist	1859-1933
1859 Moltke Moe	1887		1913	Norwegian folklorist	1859-1913
1859 Charles Diehl	1888	1888	1934	French leading authority on Byzantine art and history	1859-1944
1859 Hjalmar Falk	1888	1888	1928	Norwegian philologist and linguist	1859-1928
1859 Richard Wossidlo	1890		1922	German schoolteacher and folklorist	1859-1939
1859 Harold Whetstone Johnston	1891		1912	American classical historian and Professor of Latin	1859-1912
1859 A. E. Housman	1892		1929	British English classical scholar and poet, best known to the general public for his cycle of poems A Shropshire Lad	1859-1936
1859 Albert Curtis Clark	1892		1934	British English classical scholar, who specialised in Latin literature, Cicero, and the New Testament	1859-1937
1859 Pierre Jouguet	1893		1949	French Egyptologist and classical philologist	1869-1949
1859 Saïd Cid Kaoui	1894		1910	Algerian berberologist and lexicographer	1859-1910